

GIANT, A SOCIAL DESIGN PROJECT: ENHANCING THE BUYING EXPERIENCE IN HIGH FREQUENCY STORES (HFS) IN BOGOTÁ.

Jackeline Arango Zapata, Marcela Velásquez Montoya
Design Engineering Research Group (GRID)
Product Design Engineering Department
Universidad EAFIT, Medellín, Colombia

ABSTRACT

The Product Design Engineering Department (PDED) at Universidad EAFIT in Medellín Colombia, has been working around the concept of The Bottom of the Pyramid (BoP) in the region not only for communities with low income, but also for communities with problematical social situations. In order to use design as a discipline to solve social situations, the PDED has been developing different projects with the purpose of working with students and academics from different universities around the world, having as its main objective social innovation practices. These projects are structured to contribute to the “revolution in design” teaching as proposed by Polak (2008, p74) and transform the way design is taught with the aim of educating socially conscious students. This year (2014), twenty-five participants consisting of students and academics from Universidad EAFIT and Universidad de Los Andes (Colombia), TUDelft and The University of Amsterdam (The Netherlands), and professionals from the company Solutions Group S.A (Colombia), participated in the workshop GiANT 2014. The main goal of the project was “to enhance the buying experience in high frequency stores (HFS) in Bogotá – Colombia between the owner, the buyer, the distributor and brands, aiming for a sustainability boost of the HFS sector”. This paper outlines the project methodology and the results obtained in the two-week workshop.

KEYWORDS: *Social Innovation, Product Design Engineering (PDE), Bottom Of the Pyramid (BoP), Social Design.*

INTRODUCTION

The bottom of the pyramid (BoP) is a demographic segment composed of more than 4 billion million people around the world with annual incomes of \$2 daily (Pralhad, 2009, p.28). That is, two-thirds of humanity who remain excluded from the economic system. In addition to a low income, poverty is also manifested by a restriction of freedoms derived from belonging to a particular caste, ethnicity, gender, religion or social condition that limits opportunities for personal growth Prahalad (2011) identifies the BoP markets as a new source of radical innovation, not just in products but also in the whole business system. In Colombia, according to the latest census of The National Administrative Department of Statistics (DANE), population belonging to low-low and low income reaches 63.5% of total population (almost 50 million) in the country, and more than 80% of the total population lives on the minimum monthly salary (320 U.S Dollars).

The dynamics of today’s world impose big challenges to the people that live in it. Educational institutions – and more

specifically universities – represent the main players in society transformation, because they train the future workforce and the leaders of tomorrow. To contribute specifically to Colombian society, design projects with a social focus require activities that integrate different social, political, economic, environmental and cultural stakeholders. Acting consequently, since 2008, the Product Design Engineering Department (PDED), at Universidad EAFIT in Medellín Colombia, has been structuring projects around the concept of BoP.

In 2009 and 2010, the project “Help Manuel” took place in Medellín. Students and teaching staff from Universidad EAFIT and TUDelft worked together with small entrepreneurs from Medellín. Later in 2011, “Global Design for Kids” project was conducted with the contribution of international students from different product design engineering universities. With these past experiences, in 2012 a more mature model was created. It was called “GiANT” - Global Innovation Antioquia, an international collaboration project that aims to design, create and implement diverse services and products related to improve the quality of life of the community. During the past

six years, the developed projects congregated around 150 students, twelve academic staff, ten engineering and design professionals, seven educational institutions and ten supporting companies.

GiANT 2014 took place during two weeks and it gathered 25 participants made up of bachelor and master students; academics from different areas of the discipline of design and professionals of the industry. Different academic backgrounds and levels of participants created a diverse group: product design engineers, industrial designers, graphic designers, digital media and anthropologists. The project initiative was born with the involvement of “Solutions Group” a Colombian company with more than thirteen years of experience in Bogotá focus on the creation of Point of Purchase Advertising. Due to the company experience in the HFS (High Frequency Store) sector, Solutions Group and Universidad EAFIT proposed the 2014 project objective: “to enhance the buying experience in HFS in Bogotá between the owner, the buyer, the distributor and brands, aiming for a sustainability boost of the HFS sector”.

HFS or neighborhood stores are the top businesses in Bogotá among hair salons, restaurants, bakeries and others. The consumers prefer the assortment, variety and lend options that these stores offer compared to super and supermarkets, according to daily buying habits. According to Fernando Gonzalez, the VP of Strategic Planning of Solutions Group, in HFS exists a high level of informality in business administration and personal relations. The stores are concentrated in a higher percentage on socio economic strata one, two and three (F. Gonzalez, personal communication, 21 of June 2014).

In order to fulfill the project objective, whilst taking into account the several actors, a number of research questions were proposed to participants as a guide for the develop-

ment of the project. These questions are shown in Figure 1.

Section 2 of this paper describes GiANT project’s methodology and shows how each stage contributes to design products and services that help to enhance the buying experience in high frequency stores (HFS) in Bogotá. Section 3, summarizes the results of each team according to the design tools and techniques used. Section 4 describes project conclusions and recommendations for future initiatives.

PROJECT METHODOLOGY

Giant’s general process was defined by combining the best practices from past experiences with social design projects developed by PDED, and by recognizing the main stages of well-known methods and tools for designing and working with communities. Three specific existing methods were studied – HCD – IDEO Human Centered Design (IDEO, 2011), MCT – Market Creation Toolbox (DIBD, 2011), and CDC2 – Community Design Cooking (Arango, 2013). To accomplish the main goal and answer the research questions, the project was divided into seven stages, as shown in Figure 2: introduction, understanding, conceptualization, design, building, delivery and documentation. The project had a duration of two weeks, and during that time participants were expected to achieve the following objectives:

- Identify the needs and desires through the thoughts and feelings of the communities.
- Develop a set of project specifications for all the stakeholders: people, context and technologies.
- Explore and propose two and three dimensional solution ideas through creative questioning and experimentation,

Figure 1. Research Questions

Figure 2. GiANT process

within the guidelines of the GiANT project.

- Develop a detailed study of the ergonomics and anthropometric conditions for materials and processes that take into account concepts of sustainability and originality from a creative point of view.
- Propose a monitoring plan for the community, to involve responsible members so that the proposal is sustainable in time.

GiANT's academic staff, clustered together different tools and techniques in order to develop the process at each stage and make a selection into a "Useful toolkit" (See Figure 3) to facilitate the process according to:

- Context of immersion: two geographically defined sectors in Bogotá (Suba and Engativá)
- The HFS situation
- Lack of time (two weeks workshop)
- Different levels of academic backgrounds and knowledge of participants: bachelor students, master students and professionals.

Lectures and more detailed explanations given during the stages in order to guide the general design process. Figure 4 shows an example of detailed information of the technique

Figure 3. GiANT Useful Toolkit

the COCD Box (Byttebier & Ramon, 2009)

RESULTS

The group was divided into four teams named as follows: Group 1: Patacón Flow; Group 2: Salchichow; Group 3: Chicharrón Solvers; and Group 4: Empanadas. Figure 5 shows the main results of each group following Giant's general methodology. Focusing on enhancing the buying experience at HFS, students made presentations and physical models to share with the vendors and other important actors.

According to all project results, GiANT staff members decided to follow and continue with the implementation plan of Group 3: "The neighborhood recipe book", once the workshop was finished. For the evaluation of this proposal, a plan was made to perform a concept validation, and in this way, corroborate and document the experience generated with the proposal between the shopkeeper and customers and how it will enhance the buying experience at HFS.

The project validation consists in five stages that will be conducted according to the planned objectives and to fit the time schedule of five weeks: Week one: Discover; Week two: prototype implementation version one; Week 3: prototype re-visited; Week 4: prototype implementation version two; and Week five: editing and communicating the results

Figure 4. Description of the COCD box technique (Byttebier & Ramon, 2009 p134)

Group 1: Patacón Flows

Design Statement

“Convey the perception of freshness and better quality in high frequency stores”.

Techniques used

Understand: Observing and Interviewing, (Personas, Day in Life and Supply Chain Flow)

Conceptualize: Metaphor, Mind maps, User Profile.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting.

Build: Canvas Business Model, Prototype.

Product Concept

“De la finca a tu hogar” (*From the farm to your home*).

A platform that connects the farmers with the vendors which forms a new community (to connect the supply with the demand). This is recognizable for the buyers of the products, mainly by stickers and posters. Customers can see if a HFS is connected with the platform and will trust the freshness of the products.

Group 2: Salchichow

Design Statement

“Create visual identity to connect HFS and the community”.

Techniques used

Understand: Observing (passive and active), Interviewing (Manicure Method).

Conceptualize: Metaphor.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting and Bodystorming.

Build: Implementation plan. (Searching urban artist, searching HFS in the same neighborhood, inspired artists, artists in action, “Let them see us”, “I Belong” .

Product Concept

“Tiendarte”: A network that connects all the HFS owners through a visual resemblance achieved by local artist. An artistic work will be done on each HFS, based on the stories of the neighborhood and it will be linked to a webpage that collects all the artworks and shows the talent of the artist.

Group 3: Chicharron Solvers

Design Statement

"Create a new experience to keep and attract new customers and let the HFS seller be -the best neighbor- in the neighborhood".

Techniques used

Understand: Day in Life, Persona, Interview,

Conceptualize: Mind maps.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting.

Build: Prototypes.

Product Concept

"El recetario de barrio" (*The neighborhood recipe book*)

A product that includes a set of cards, that can be filled in by the customers of the HFS with a recipe. The idea is to create a social recipe huddle that allows a free exchange of recipes. The ingredients could be purchased at the HFS. It helps to have better relationships tender-customers and increase sales according to be a cheap and seasonable ingredients.

Group 4: Empanada

Design Statement

"Create a shop-layout in HFS that goes with the daily routine of the customer".

Techniques used

Understand: Observing and Interviewing.

Conceptualize: Mind maps, User profile.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting and Bodystorming.

Build: Prototype, storyboards.

Product Concept

The concept consist of two aspects: (i) a tool to measure the sales and (ii) a unit to display the products:

1. An app for a tablet or smartphone that helps the tender to keep track of who buys what and in what moment.
2. The display is designed to display the products in a really easy way. All the products can be displayed in crates to enable to tender to move the products easily.

CONCLUSIONS

This article describes GiANT 2014 as a social design project centered on the experience gained on previous projects developed (Help Manuel, GDK and GiANT) by the PDED at Universidad EAFIT and the collaboration between a variety of academic staff members of different universities and Solutions Group S.A as an industry partner. Different academic backgrounds and levels of participants created a diverse group that allowed a rich experimentation with an exchange of design techniques and methods that challenge every participant to analyze and expand their own approach to social design projects. Although a selection of tools were given to participants, depending on the level of knowledge on this and the expertise on the HFS topic, each group decided to use the tools that worked for them, and which will guide them best through the design process.

As an international collaboration project, GiANT creates an opportunity to redefine professional careers with a more open-minded approach according to discoveries about the culture, social differences, language barriers, and design perspectives etc. The intense workshop was a great opportunity for participants to get a detailed overview of the cultural context of the two selected sectors in Bogotá (Suba and Engativá), and in this way, to gain inspiration and to experiment with different tools and techniques in order to design for a specific community. One of the key elements is that the immersion in context allows a better understanding of the authentic community needs and, as a consequence, a better design solution that will impact positively on the community involved.

Participants were invited to live, work and play together on an everyday basis in an unfamiliar environment. They learned how to deal with uncertainty in so far as not everything was written on the project guide or given to them in detail in order to succeed in the process. The learning experience expands beyond the lecture rooms into every aspect of their lives. The project offers new challenges for students, academic staff and the industry. Participants can live in other cultures and explore their design, industrial and commercial processes. Universities and Industry could collaborate

like this in other topics towards a common goal and, in this way, promote students and professionals in the industry with a more international education with a social responsibility vision. Some limitations of the realization of this project included: an heterogeneous group with different professional stages (undergraduate, master students, professionals, and academics) that demanded to have a clear common goal, had to deal with language as a barrier of communication within each team, as well as with the community involved.

Project validation is a required phase that, due to the lack of time during the project, should be developed after the workshop with a clear refinement of responsibilities from the authors and the involved actors.

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